

LINGUISTIC STATUS OF ANTHROPNOMS

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ABSTRACT

This article deals with the linguistic status of anthroponyms, which occupy a special place in lexical system of language. This factual perspective is determined by specific features of proper names including grammatical, historical and semantic peculiarities. Being an integral part of the life of any person, personal names, as part of the language system, have attracted the attention of researchers for a long time. Hence, the problem of the conception of anthroponyms and its status in the lexical system is vital and actual at the present time.

Anthroponyms are proper names which denoting people; they fulfil key functions in linguistic system and reflect sociocultural features of a society. The linguistic status of anthroponyms is defined by various aspects, such as functions, structure, dynamics, sociocultural significance, linguacultural aspect and others.

In any language anthroponyms take a special place so that they connect native speakers with linguistic community. Anthroponyms have double meaning: it acts as a classifying marker, indicating one or another position of an individual in the social structure, at the same time as a symbol mirroring a certain vision of the world, as well as an organized system of beliefs and perceptions.

An anthroponym is a type of proper name that is officially assigned to an individual representative of society as his or her identifying sign. Anthroponymy of a language is a set of anthroponyms functioning in it. Anthroponymy is the section of onomastics that studies anthroponyms. Anthroponymy serves as a historical, ethnographic and sociological source that helps to identify a great number of factors about the culture, mode of life, linguistic creativity, beliefs of certain community that speaks the language.

Linguists investigate the features of anthroponyms as a linguistic category of language, the structure of their semantics, the features of the functioning of anthroponyms in speech and language. The popular issue is the study of the functioning of proper names in artistic discourse, the sociolinguistic motivation of anthroponyms, the means and methods of expressing the connotative meaning of names. Anthroponyms can be analyzed in their formal and nonformal

forms, their differentiation from stylistic point of view, also the productivity of the formation of names and territorial and social dialectal anthroponyms are taken into consideration.

There are the following functions of anthroponyms: communicative, expressive, dialectal and appellative. Accumulative function is characterized for proper names, the function is connected with the ability of proper names to have a sociocultural seme in the meaning of a word and linguacultural information in its semantic structure. Proper names do not have grammatical and lexical functions, one of their functions is legalization of their owner in appropriate society.

Anthroponyms are involved in the main function of language – communicative. Without anthroponyms, communication between people is impossible or very complicated. In the process of communication, we very often use proper names as integral elements of our thinking. Anthroponyms also perform a phatic function, which helps to establish contact with the addressee. Often, in order to establish contact, a person begins to call the addressee by name, checking whether he hears him. Together with the phatic function, the appellative function is also involved, when the addressee uses the addresser's name as an address. It is extremely vital for us to consider the expressive function of language, which is often performed by proper names, especially anthroponyms. This is clearly visible in some languages in the various uses of name forms, since this function can be performed not only with the help of lexical, but also with the help of word-formation means. Proper names also have a deictic function. It means that they have the function of indication like personal pronouns or demonstrative pronouns. If we consider specific anthroponyms we should consider the role-deixis, which indicate the participants of a speech act.

As a consequence, in the linguistic status anthroponyms refer to the category of onyms, what is more they (anthroponyms) have the features and functions of onomastic lexis. Additionally, anthroponyms differ from other onomastic units, they are units with semantics.

Anthroponyms are not just signs of identification, they are as a “mirror” of the culture, history and social process. The investigation of anthroponyms let us understand how appropriate language reflects and forms an identity of a person or society.

The main difference between proper name and common noun is the connection between proper name with concept and subject. The connection between a word, a concept and a subject are usually depicted as a triangle. The triangle symbolizes a connection between extralinguistic denotation(subject), linguistic, logical and semantic image.

The semantics of proper names involves sociocultural information which makes it (semantics) much more complicated. Due to their close connection with what they denote, because without this connection proper names cannot be thought of, proper names have a weakened conceptual connection.

Theoretical approach of some researchers in definition of the conceptual scope of proper names is based on the concept, according to which the meaning of the anthroponomical lexis is analyzed as a structure consists of two parts: the intention, which is a core of the meaning and the implication which is an extra meaning. The intentional part of the meaning is the concept of proper name itself, while the implicational of proper names consists of various parts. The implicational is an encyclopedic characteristic of an anthroponyms, and the result of this is the influence of some extralinguistic factors on its meaning and functioning. In speech just some

features of proper names can be actualized which can form its weak implicational. Dealing with a strong implicational it is vital to mention that it is a correlation with a certain class of proper names.

It follows that proper name is a unit of language which have the concept of single meaning in its core, so it is obtained with its denotative meaning. Thus , according to some theories the meaning of a proper names includes: -semantic core, intentional , which conforms to the structural significance of the onym (proper name), - strong implication, which consist of relevant features of a name in a certain language, - weak implication, which can be actualized in the process of speech communication, and also - negative implication, seme which cannot characterize the denotation of the meaning of a proper name (onym).

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